

Space Artificial Structure for Solar Panels

Putting in space an artificial structure with solar panels for sunlight collection can enable humanity to fuel most of its energy needs in the future. After setting up the structure, we can beam energy directly to earth using lasers. The economic benefits for this procedure will be enormous since we can use far more space in orbit than on the surface of Earth.

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